

Ideal Quantum Coin Tossing is Asymmetrically Possible

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Abstract: It has been claimed that ideal quantum coin tossing is impossible, both symmetrically and asymmetrically. The claim is partly based on the assumption that the shared entangled state cannot be verified. This assumption perhaps challenges the very foundation of quantum mechanics. However, the claim has been widely accepted. Here, we show that ideal quantum coin tossing is asymmetrically possible. In other words, in a two-party quantum coin-tossing protocol, zero bias against cheating can be achieved by one party.

In this world, cheating cannot be completely ruled out in any situation. For example, the outcome of a real coin toss cannot be regarded as completely trustworthy. However, in 1981, Blum optimistically introduced [1] the idea of ideal coin tossing, in which two mutually mistrustful parties seek to generate bias-free outcomes, that is, unconditionally secure outcomes.

Coin tossing is not only a problem of cryptography and game theory; it has broad implications. It basically asks whether collective measurement and observation, on which scientific knowledge is built, can be unconditionally secure against cheating. Be that as it may, it was realized [2] that ideal classical coin tossing is impossible. With the advent of quantum cryptography [3], it was natural to expect that, just as quantum key distribution can achieve unconditional security against eavesdropping through the no-cloning principle [4,5], quantum coin tossing (QCT) could likewise achieve unconditional security against cheating by virtue of the same no-cloning principle.

However, it has been claimed [6] that ideal QCT is impossible even under ideal conditions. In other words, it has been claimed that, in a two-party QCT protocol, zero bias against cheating cannot be achieved either by both parties symmetrically or by a single party asymmetrically. The same claim has subsequently been made [7,8].

The claim is based partly on the assumption that the shared EPR state cannot be verified [6] and partly on the no-go theorem, which states that unconditionally secure quantum bit commitment (QBC) is

impossible [9,10] (bit commitment is another fundamental cryptographic task related to coin tossing). The claim [6–8] has been widely accepted in the literature [11–14].

In a two-party quantum protocol, if the entanglement of shared EPR states [15] cannot be verified, then violations of Bell inequalities [16] cannot be collectively or individually verified with unconditional security against cheating. In a two-party quantum protocol, if measurement outcomes cannot be verified with unconditional security against cheating, quantum randomness cannot be collectively or individually verified with unconditional security against cheating. Surprisingly, the implications of the claim [6–8] have never been addressed in the literature. As a result, the claim [6–8] did not face any rigorous scientific scrutiny.

To address this problem, we observed [17,18] that shared EPR singlet states can be verified because the singlet state is rotationally invariant. Therefore, one may consider using verified singlet states to prevent cheating in QCT. However, the no-go theorem states that entanglement can itself be exploited for cheating. Thus, a paradoxical situation arises: entanglement is required to prevent cheating, yet the same entanglement can also be used to cheat. This is a Catch-22 situation. To overcome this Catch-22 situation, we must somehow bypass the no-go theorem.

The no-go theorem is based on a fundamental principle of quantum mechanics: any possible quantum state ψ can be transformed into another possible quantum state ϕ by a suitable unitary operation assisted by entanglement. Conventional QBC protocols employ such possible quantum states. Consequently, the encoded states can be manipulated during the execution of the protocol due to this fundamental principle. The no-go theorem therefore assumes that QBC protocols necessarily operate on possible quantum states ψ and ϕ .

We shall see that, using the same fundamental quantum principle, one party can convert a pure entangled state into a mixed entangled state ρ , while the other party remains unaware of how ρ was prepared. Through unitary operations, entanglement can be remotely locked and unlocked by converting a pure entangled state into the mixed entangled state ρ , and vice versa. The state ρ remains single-blind to the other party due to the density-matrix indistinguishability (DMI) principle [19], which is complementary to the no-cloning principle [4,5]. If the QCT protocol is performed using the single-blind mixed entangled state ρ , the no-go theorem is no longer applicable. Specifically, the other party cannot manipulate ρ through the same entanglement-assisted unitary transformation.

To prepare the SB mixed entangled state ρ , let us first consider the following four EPR-Bell states of a pair of spin-1/2 particles.

$$|\Psi_{\pm}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|01\rangle \pm |10\rangle)$$

$$|\Phi_{\pm}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle \pm |11\rangle)$$

where 0 and 1 denote two opposite spin directions. Let us recall the well-known identity: $\sigma_x^2 = \sigma_y^2 = \sigma_z^2 = \mathbf{I}^2 = \mathbf{I}$ where $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$ are three Pauli matrices and \mathbf{I} is 2×2 identity matrix. This identity implies that EPR-Bell states will remain *invariant*, if the same $U_i \in \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z, \mathbf{I}\}$ is doubly

applied to one particle of an EPR-Bell pair. The transformation of EPR singlets $|\Psi_{-}\rangle_i$ under the double unitary operations following the above identity may be depicted as

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\psi_{-}\rangle &\xrightarrow{\sigma_x} |\varphi_{-}\rangle \xrightarrow{\sigma_x} |\psi_{-}\rangle \\
 |\psi_{-}\rangle &\xrightarrow{\sigma_y} |\varphi_{+}\rangle \xrightarrow{\sigma_y} |\psi_{-}\rangle \\
 |\psi_{-}\rangle &\xrightarrow{\sigma_z} |\psi_{+}\rangle \xrightarrow{\sigma_z} |\psi_{-}\rangle \\
 |\psi_{-}\rangle &\xrightarrow{I} |\psi_{-}\rangle \xrightarrow{I} |\psi_{-}\rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

One party, say Alice, wishes to ensure that the other party, say Bob, cannot introduce any bias. We now present the quantum coin-tossing protocol.

1. Alice invites Bob to prepare EPR singlet states.
2. Bob prepares EPR singlet states $|\Psi_{-}\rangle_i$. He sends one particle from each pair to Alice and stores its partner in his quantum memory.
3. Alice randomly applies a unitary operator U_i^A from $\{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z, I\}$ on her particles and keeps them in her quantum memory. The resulting states are $|\varphi_{-}\rangle_i$, $|\varphi_{+}\rangle_i$, $|\Psi_{+}\rangle_i$ and $|\Psi_{-}\rangle_i$.
4. Alice randomly selects some particles and asks Bob to send their partners. Bob sends the particles to Alice.
5. Alice converts the selected pairs into singlets by applying the same unitary operator U_i^A from $\{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z, I\}$.
6. Alice measures the spin components of the selected pairs in her randomly chosen basis. If she obtains perfectly correlated data, the entanglement of the shared states is verified. After the verification, she proceeds to the next step.
7. Bob measures the spin component of his remaining particles along the z-axis. He reveals his measurement outcomes.
8. Alice measures the spin component of her remaining particles along z-axis. She reveals her measurement outcomes.
9. Alice finally reveals the unitary operators U_i^A .
10. Alice and Bob will check whether their measurement outcomes are perfectly correlated.

The density matrix of their shared EPR-Bell states after the first round of transformation may be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\rho^A &= \frac{1}{4} (|\psi_-\rangle\langle\psi_-| + |\psi_+\rangle\langle\psi_+| + |\phi_-\rangle\langle\phi_-| + |\phi_+\rangle\langle\phi_+|) \\
&= \frac{1}{8} [(|01\rangle - |10\rangle)(\langle 01| - \langle 10|) + (|01\rangle + |10\rangle)(\langle 01| + \langle 10|) + (|00\rangle - |11\rangle)(\langle 00| - \langle 11|) + (|00\rangle + |11\rangle)(\langle 00| + \langle 11|)] \\
&= \frac{1}{4} I, \text{ where } I \text{ is } 4 \times 4 \text{ identity matrix.}
\end{aligned}$$

Alice suppresses entanglement of the shared EPR-Bell states in ρ^A , which is a maximally mixed SB state. Alice reveals her U_i^A only after Bob's results have been disclosed. This means that ρ^A remains SB state to Bob until the end of the protocol.

Coin tossing protocols are designed to generate outcomes 0 and 1 with probabilities P_0 and P_1 , respectively, where $P_0 = P_1 = 1/2 + \epsilon_A/\epsilon_B$, and ϵ_A and ϵ_B denote the biases introduced by Alice and Bob, respectively.

Let us examine the present protocol. Since Bob does not know which U_i^A Alice will apply to which EPR-Bell states, the entanglement is completely suppressed in ρ^A due to DMI principle. But, Bob can initially mix any single-particle spin polarized states $|\chi\rangle$ with singlet states and send them to Alice. While applying U_i^A to the singlets Alice will unknowingly apply U_i^A to $|\chi\rangle$ as well, and thereby converting $|\chi\rangle$ into unpolarized state $\rho^a = \frac{1}{2}I$. All information about $|\chi\rangle$ is totally lost in $\rho^a = \frac{1}{2}I$ due to DMI principle. Therefore, this strategy of Bob will fail. Bob cannot bias any outcome. As Alice discloses her results and U_i^A only after Bob has disclosed his U_i^B Alice can easily reveal fabricated data and thereby completely bias the measurement outcomes. The protocol ensures, $\epsilon_B = 0$, $\epsilon_A = 1/2$. Ideal quantum coin tossing can be realized asymmetrically.

Around 2002, the idea of weak quantum coin tossing was formally introduced [13] without refuting the claim [6–8] that ideal (strong) quantum coin tossing is impossible. In weak quantum coin tossing, cheating is somewhat restricted by the rules of the game. Our results imply that zero bias in weak quantum coin tossing can also be achieved asymmetrically.

It is possible to bypass the no-go theorem. The protocol follows the standard qubit model of quantum encoding. We observed that there are some limitations of the standard qubit model in information processing. To achieve ideal QCT symmetrically [20], we followed an alternative quantum coding scheme [21].

In conclusion, the present scheme demonstrates that dishonesty can be prevented at the level of a single qubit. In this sense, honesty is the best policy in quantum coin tossing. Entanglement serves as a scientific moral compass. This result is encouraging, since in the real world, dishonesty can never be

completely prevented. The scientific community itself is not immune to this ethical problem (scientific misconduct, blocking scientific work for self-interest, etc.). The scheme may also provide an instructive example for discussing the relationship between scientific principles, trust, and ethics in educational institutions.

Apart from cryptography, there is one implication of this work. Since, in a two-party quantum protocol, one party can generate measurement outcomes with unconditional security against cheating, one party can verify quantum randomness with unconditional security against cheating. It perhaps implies that, in a two-party experiment, one party can verify quantum mechanics unconditionally.

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